

REDUCING ACCIDENTS ON EXPRESSWAYS: A DEEP LEARNING BASED DRIVER HYPNOSIS ALERT SYSTEM TO REDUCE ACCIDENTS ON EXPRESSWAYS

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Abstract

The rapid development of road infrastructure, particularly expressways, has significantly improved transportation efficiency by reducing travel time. However, the increased frequency of accidents on these roads has raised safety concerns. According to statistics from the Indian Ministry of Road Transport and Highways, around 1.5 lakh people lose their lives on Indian roads each year. Surprisingly, an emerging cause of these accidents is attributed to "Driver Hypnotism." Long, congestion-free highways are believed to alter the state of mind of drivers, leading them into an unconscious state with their eyes open. This research proposes a deep learning-based model designed to efficiently detect driver hypnotism and implement appropriate countermeasures to reduce the likelihood of accidents on highways. The result shows that the accuracy rates of 71% in simulated driving experiments is obtained. The proposed method was compared with k-nearest neighbor (KNN) and random forest (RF). The results showed that the proposed model had better performance. This research provides a novel and convenient method to realize the driver's road hypnosis detection function of the intelligent driver assistance system in practical applications.

Keywords: Hypnosis, Expressways, Deep Learning Model, CNN, Accident Detection, EAR.

1. INTRODUCTION

Nowadays India is expanding its road infrastructure by connecting various cities with long-distance highways. As per the survey by the National Highway Authority of India (NHAI) on National Highways, driver hypnotism is the prime reason for accidents on highways. Driver hypnosis, also termed as white line fever, is a mental state of a driver, in which a driver drives a vehicle without having any awareness of doing so. So it is of utmost importance to identify such abnormal behavior of a driver to prevent a colossal accident. The advanced driver assistance system has considered the many human attributes that mainly affect driver state performance (Tosi, J. D, et.al.,2020) like driver emotion, driver intention, driver tendency of driving, and driver's behavioral pattern. Numerous research findings considered parameters like distracted driving, emotional driving, fatigue driving, and drunk driving to detect the driver's abnormal driving state. One of the most difficult tasks in the field of intelligent transportation is to thoroughly comprehend the numerous types of characteristic information about the driver and to precisely determine the particular mental state of the driver.

Escalation in the studies of road safety affirms that intervention of driver factors is more important to study for robust intelligent transport system development. This driver factor study is a multidisciplinary field that consists of ergonomics, cognitive neuroscience, machine vision, sensor networks, deep learning, etc. The Driver's mindset can be categorized as drowsy, fatigued, distracted, attentive, hypnotized (looked but not seen), and unknown. Many researchers have put forth the techniques to detect the distracted and fatigued state of a driver. However, there are only a few studies that have concentrated on the hypnotized state of the driver. Detection of the hypnotized state of the driver is of utmost importance as long-distance highways push drivers mainly into a hypnotized state, which results in massive accidents. Driver hypnosis forces the driver to enter into a trance-linked mental state in which he experiences decreased vigilance, loss of attention, experiences illusion, and transient memory loss which lead to comatose driving (Shi, H., t.al.,2023) therefore, if the accident happens in such a hypnotized state of a driver then it is much more intense than the conventional accidents. Hence it is foremost important to promote safe driving by detecting the driver's hypnotism at the right time with greater accuracy.

Driver hypnosis is difficult to detect as compared to driver distraction and driver fatigue as in fatigued and distracted driver performs some noticeable body transitions like yawning, abnormal body posture, frequent eye blinking, etc. Nevertheless, in driver hypnosis, the driver will be looking straight without noticeable changes in body posture and facial expression.

Hence this paper puts forth the robust and accurate driver hypnosis detection model which will detect the driver hypnosis and perform the counter measure respectively. The proposed system uses the convolutional neural network (CNN) to train the model. The system considers the variation in driving patterns and facial expressions and accurately detects hypnotism with greater efficiency and accuracy.

2. LITERATURE SURVEY

The highway hypnosis is a curse to infrastructural development. Driver hypnosis is the main cause of terrible accidents on highways resulting in hampering road safety. As per the literature survey performed in this paper, Highway hypnosis was first discovered in 1921 which was further put forth by (Williams et.al.,1963) with a clear distinction between hypnosis and sleep. The researchers put forth the concept that the oculomotor system (the neurological system responsible for the initiation of eye movements) is related to driver hypnosis. Also the researchers (Wertheim et.al.1978) performed some experimentation to decide that driver hypnosis is a neurological problem. However, they suggested further rigorous experimentation to verify the influence of other parameters on driver hypnosis and misbehaved drivers. To improve road safety states that the accurate detection of driving behavior is of utmost importance, the paper (Yang,S et.al.,2019) further enlisted the features to inculcate self and safe driving. Authors of (Cerezuela, et.al.,2004) support partial hypnotism; nevertheless, their results emphasize the drowsiness on motorways rather than on conventional roads. Authors of (Alameen et.al.,2023) detected the highway hypnosis using the PCA-LSTM model. To categorize normal driving with highway hypnosis, the authors use 50 test subjects to perform experimentation.

The Convolutional neural network is capable of extracting and processing spatial features. Researchers (Alameen et.al.,2023) combine CNN and LSTM to build the spatiotemporal model to detect driver drowsiness. The efforts had been put up by many researchers mainly to detect the driver drowsiness system, among them authors of (Kassem, et.al.,2020) detect the drowsiness based on yawning dataset. The authors classify the driver's state as fatigue, early fatigue, and awake. The authors (Kongcharoen, et.al.,2020) developed the CNN-based model to analyze the driver's behavior as sleepy or awake. The model claims 94% accuracy in detecting whether the driver feels sleepy or not based on eye movement whether open or closed. Further authors have the hybrid and hierarchical model put forth by the researchers of (S. Jamshidi, et.al., 2021) uses CNN with LSTM to detect drowsiness using the face, eyes, and mouth posture detection. The model detects the driver's drowsiness with an accuracy of 87.19%.

Table 1: Literature Survey

Authors	Models	Dataset	Features	Results and accuracy
(Wertheim et.al.1978)	Spectral & Statistical	Actual dataset of 14 drivers	ECG activity data specifically based on eye performance	Authors Specifically proved that driver drowsiness than driver hypnotism on highways.
(Yang,S et.al.,2019)	Random forest	30 skilled drivers tested on a driving simulator	Distance and velocity. Authors also use the features set like lane-related features, Driver related features,gap-	The model assists in choosing features for self and safe driving.

			related feature	
(Cerezuela, et.al.,2004)	Statistical Model	Actual Road data on A-7 Motorways and N-340 road A-7 motorway and the N-340 road in the Valencian Community (Spain). The authors have collected the data in the same weather conditions and the same light conditions in the daytime only. Moreover at the time of data collection drivers are instructed to maintain the speed between 100 and 120 km/h.	Electroencephalography (EEG) signals of the drivers and eye recordings were observed	The authors partially support driver hypnosis. However, Authors claim that drowsiness is more common on highways
(Alameen et.al.,2023)	3D CNN and LSTM	Multimodal Multiview and Multispectral Driver Action Dataset (3MDAD) and YawDD	Drowsiness-related spatiotemporal features of the driver's face	The model is used to detect drowsiness with an accuracy of 96%
(Kassem, et.al.,2020)	CNN	YawDD with 322 subjects(Drivers data)	Driver facial features particularly yawning images.	Authors detected the driver fatigue with an accuracy of 96.2%
(Kongcharoen, et.al.,2020)	CNN-Haar Cascade algorithm	Facial dataset	eye position and eye gaze	The authors implemented the driver drowsiness system alert method. However exact accuracy is not specified by the authors.
(S. Jamshidi, et.al.,2021)	CNN and LSTM	NTHU-DDD dataset	Face, mouth, and eye	Detect the driver's drowsiness with an accuracy of 87.19%

The literature survey reveals that many researchers put forth their studies regarding the detection of driver fatigue, driver distraction, driver drowsiness, misbehaved driving, etc. However, there is very limited research on the detection of driver hypnosis. Driver distraction, drowsiness, and fatigue mainly happen because of driver internal body changes like sleep deprivation, hypertension, excessive driving, etc. On the other hand, driver hypnosis majorly depends upon external manifestation of the road. During driving the driver's hypnosis makes the driver unconscious and the driver doesn't recall the situation in the vehicle or on the road causing a massive accident that is far more dangerous and destructive than conventional accidents. Therefore, the design of a driver hypnosis detection system with an alert mechanism is certainly needed to impose road safety. The following section discusses the system model for driver hypnosis detection.

3. PROPOSED METHODOLOGY

Driver hypnosis is of prime concern to ensure safety on highways. The driver hypnosis detection system specified in this paper used two real-time cameras, one for detecting the state of an eye and the other to read the parameters of the steering and accelerometer. The proposed convolution network is shown in Figure -1. The network uses the images of the height I_h and width of I_w then fed to the convolution network. The pooling is done using the filters of the size of $F_h * F_w$ with the stride size S . The output image size will be generated using equation 1. The padding is used to maintain the output image size equal to the input image size. The max pooling strategy is used with a kernel size of $2 * 2$ and with a stride of size 2. The features extracted by the previous convolutional layer and the maximum pooling layer are integrated by the fully connected layer. Softmax function is used to classify the exact state of the eye to detect the hypnosis

$$\text{Output image} = (I_h - F_h + S) * (I_w - F_w + S) \text{-----} 1$$

Figure 1: Proposed Model: Driver Hypnosis Detection

Driver Hypnosis Detection:

The proposed system uses the two stages for driver hypnosis detection. The first stage is Eye localization techniques. However, the second stage is the eye state detection technique and the final stage is detection of the hypnotism.

Stage 1: Eye Localization Technique.

The proposed method first locates the eyes from the captured face image using a cascade convolution network model (Sun, Y, et.al.,2013). During the training and testing phase, this model provides excellent computational complexity. To detect the face, the proposed method marks the 15 facial points on the captured image as shown in the following Figure 1. Facial landmark detection is a computer vision task that can be done using an inbuilt Dlib library. The Dlib library provides the support to implement deep learning and computer vision techniques.

The proposed method uses the 15 facial landmark points from Dlib (Kazemi, V. et.al.,2014). A pre-trained facial landmark detection known as Max-Margin (MMOD) CNN face detector from the Dlib package was used to estimate the 15 (x,y)-coordinates on the face that corresponds to the facial structure. Figure 1 displays that the eyebrows point as points from 1 to 4. Points 5 to 10 locate eyes. Point 11 depicts the nose and points 12,13,14,15 locates the mouth. The Max-Margin (MMOD) CNN face detector first locates the face and returns the output as a rectangle over a detected face as shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Facial Points

Figure 3: Face Detection

Stage -2: Eye State Detection

This paper uses computer vision to detect the driver's hypnosis. The proposed method calculates the eye aspect ratio (EAR) as given in eq-1, which is a scalar quantity to detect the state of an eye open or closed. When the driver blinks the eyes it leads to a swift increase and decrease in the EAR ratio. The proposed method uses the 0.3 as EAR threshold (Rakshita, R. 2018) to distinguish between open and closed eyes.

Figure 4: EAR Detection

There is a sudden drop notice when the driver closes the eyes, however, the EAR returns to normal value when the driver opens the eyes. This paper uses a robust and simple method to calculate EAR, which will be precisely used to detect the open and closed eye states.

The proposed method plots the eye in a 2D plane along the x and y-axis. The points P, Q, R, and S shown in the figure -4 have the (x, y) coordinates. The x-axis values determine the width of an eye; however, the y-axis determines the height of an eye. To determine the eye open state, the distance along the y-axis must be maximum, however, to determine the eye close state the distance along the y-axis must be minimum (≈ 0). The EAR is calculated using the equation 2. Nonetheless, the following equations 3 and 4 can be used to detect the EAR open and EAR closed respectively.

$$\begin{aligned} \text{EAR} &= \text{distance} [(x_0, y_1)(x_0, y_2)] = \text{distance} (y_1, y_2) \text{-----} 2 \\ &= || y_1 - y_2 || \end{aligned}$$

$$\text{EAR Open} = \max (|| y_1 - y_2 ||) \text{-----} 3$$

$$\text{EAR Close} = \min (|| y_1 - y_2 ||) \text{-----} 4$$

Stage 3: Hypnosis Detection

Driver hypnosis, also known as white line fever, represents a lowered awareness and attention state that can happen while traveling long distances on monotonous and familiar routes, such as highways. It is a form of altered awareness that can happen while driving far-flung, unchanged highways.

Driver hypnosis may cause people to appear alert and have open eyes i.e. affecting the oculomotor system, but their cognitive function and attentiveness may deteriorate. This leads to massive accidents. The following flowchart of figure-5 depicts the proposed process of hypnosis detection.

Figure 5: Flowchart for Hypnosis Detection

The proposed algorithm uses the MRL dataset which contains the facial data of 37 people out of which 33 men and 4 women. The dataset contains 84,898 images annotated using the following annotations given in following table 2.

Table 2: Annotation Details

Sr. No.	Annotation	Details
1	subject ID	Data collected from 37 persons
2	image ID	Data is collected for 84,898 Persons
3	Gender	0-Men 1-Women
4	Glasses	0-No 1-Yes
5	Eye State	0-Closed 1-Open
6	Light Condition	0-Good 1-Bad
7	Reflections	0-None 1-Small 2-Big

After annotating the images, the facial landmark points are captured and the algorithm detects the face. Once the face is detected successfully, for detection of eyes the algorithm calculates the eye aspect ratio (EAR).

This calculated EAR is compared with the previously set threshold of open eyes and closed eyes. If the calculated EAR is greater than the threshold, then eyes open else eyes close. When the driver blinks the eyes the EAR drops to zero.

The hypnosis phase decreases the eye moment of the driver. As per the survey conducted by (Weitzenhoffer, 1969) for the behavior of eyes and hypnosis. It was found that the eye blink rate (EBR) decreased significantly.

This implies that the hypnosis phase either leads to eyes open or eyes closed for a longer duration of time. Hence the proposed technique uses the two-time counters (t) for eyes open (to) and eyes closed (tc). The initial value of both counters is zero.

To reduce the false positive ratio, every time the algorithm detects the eye open or eye closed, the counter (to) and (tc) incremented. If the counter reaches a threshold value (6) it rings an alarm for the first time, this signifies that the driver's eyes are open for a longer duration of time. To avoid the driver reaching up to the hypnosis phase the alarm rings for the first time with lower intensity.

Furthermore, if the counter reaches to next threshold (8), it alarms for a second time and if the counter reaches to final threshold values (10) then finally hypnosis is detected. The proposed method states the continuous sound alarming system which will help the driver to come up from the hypnosis phase and ultimately reduce the accidents.

4. RESULT & DISCUSSION

Driver hypnosis detection plays a vital role in the prevention of accidents. The proposed method uses the MRL data set for model calibration, training, and verification. A deep learning approach using the CNN algorithm is used to implement the model. In this section, the proposed model is tested and the experimental results are analyzed for its level of accuracy. CNN classifies images effectively by using several convolution processes and offers scalable features for very big data sets. It is evident from Fig. 1 that the multi-layer CNN performs better at classifying the multi-layer state of the driver and forecasting the driver's state. Increasing the processing time or epochs increases the classifier's accuracy level. One noteworthy aspect of this driver hypnosis detection system is that it needs to have a minimum time to identify driver hypnotism. The overall accuracy of the model as shown in figure-6 is 71% with 10 epochs. In future, the accuracy can be increased with lesser processing time

Epoch 1/10

1563/1563 [=====] - 78s 49ms/step - loss: 1.5178 - accuracy: 0.4465 - val_loss: 1.2276 - val_accuracy: 0.5602

Epoch 2/10

1563/1563 [=====] - 75s 48ms/step - loss: 1.1439 - accuracy: 0.5957 - val_loss: 1.0578 - val_accuracy: 0.6279

Epoch 3/10

1563/1563 [=====] - 77s 49ms/step - loss: 0.9891 - accuracy: 0.6549 - val_loss: 0.9838 - val_accuracy: 0.6552

Epoch 4/10

1563/1563 [=====] - 81s 52ms/step - loss: 0.8857 - accuracy: 0.6897 - val_loss: 0.9600 - val_accuracy: 0.6669

Epoch 5/10

1563/1563 [=====] - 74s 47ms/step - loss: 0.8178 - accuracy: 0.7112 - val_loss: 0.9411 - val_accuracy: 0.6728

Epoch 6/10

1563/1563 [=====] - 76s 48ms/step - loss: 0.7526 - accuracy: 0.7362 - val_loss: 0.8793 - val_accuracy: 0.6990

Epoch 7/10

1563/1563 [=====] - 72s 46ms/step - loss: 0.7046 - accuracy: 0.7528 - val_loss: 0.9072 - val_accuracy: 0.6964

Epoch 8/10

1563/1563 [=====] - 76s 49ms/step - loss: 0.6646 - accuracy: 0.7677 - val_loss: 0.8409 - val_accuracy: 0.7164

Epoch 9/10

1563/1563 [=====] - 72s 46ms/step - loss: 0.6208 - accuracy: 0.7824 - val_loss: 0.8873 - val_accuracy: 0.7013

Epoch 10/10

1563/1563 [=====] - 79s 51ms/step - loss: 0.5838 - accuracy: 0.7939 - val_loss: 0.9283 - val_accuracy: 0.7000

Figure 6: Accuracy Graph of the proposed System

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